

PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS FOR THE FORMATION OF AGGRESSIVE BEHAVIOR IN THE YOUTH ENVIRONMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10365648>

Abstract. *An urgent problem of modern society is the increase in aggressive behavior in the youth environment. Heteroaggression is manifested in the form of quarrels, robberies, robberies, murders, etc., autoaggression – suicide, chemical and non-chemical drugs, extreme sports, etc. many scientific works are devoted to the search for social causes of the current situation.*

Keywords: *aggressive behavior, youth environment, psychological factors, autoaggression.*

Introduction. In modern society, there is an increase in aggression in the youth environment. The heteroaggressiveness of young people is manifested in the form of violence against other people and animals, rudeness in speech, the application of acts of violence to the weak, even to beatings and murder. Autoaggressiveness is manifested in the form of suicide and parasuicides directly consciously causing self-harm or unconsciously-extreme sports, substance abuse [1-3].

Nevertheless, the exact definition of aggression has not yet been developed. In different literary sources, definitions can be found that characterize this phenomenon from different sides [4].

1. Aggression is an active negative action, thought, or action aimed at harming a particular object and/or protecting one's own interests [5].

2. V. P. Zinchenko and B. G. According to the "psychological dictionary" edited by Meshcheryakov, aggression is motivational destructive behavior (negative experience, state of tension, fear, depression, etc.) that contradicts the norms (rules) of joint life of people in society, harms the objects of attack (live and inanimate), physically harms people or causes them psychological discomfort [6].

3. In modern national American English dictionaries: aggression is an unjustified attack; invasion; the usual use of aggressive behavior; basic instinct, usually associated with the emotional background necessary to carry out an action of a violent nature. An act of violence or style of action (as an unprovoked attack) is carried out with the intention of dominating or submitting. Aggressive behavior is considered hostile, harmful, or destructive. Aggressiveness is the probability of behavior caused by frustration [7].

Currently, the scientific community has abandoned the search for a single universal cause of aggressive behavior in the youth environment [8].

The crises taking place in the modern world have a negative impact on individuals of different ages. Especially the younger generation is exposed to such an effect. During the formation of conscious behavior, personal orientation, moral ideas and social relationships [9-11]. In domestic and foreign psychology, the problem of aggression is solved depending on the goals of its researchers. Currently, scientists dealing with the problem of aggression and aggression have different positions in assessing the pros and cons of this phenomenon [12-14]. This is due to the

extreme complexity and polymorphism of the manifestation of aggression. The current situation determines that there are different interpretations of the concepts of "aggression" and "aggression" [4, 5]. One important aspect of defining these concepts is that it has an interdisciplinary character. The phenomenon of aggression is the subject of the study of social and Natural Sciences. In the modern scientific world, it is customary to consider aggression as a polyetiological phenomenon, the reasons for its manifestation can be both biological and social, psychological factors. Accordingly, knowledge from various scientific disciplines should be used to reveal the essence of the concepts of "aggression", "aggression", "aggressive behavior". This is important in order to get a complete picture of what is happening to a guy or girl who shows disruptive aggression in society [15-17].

Currently, aggressive behavior is very common among young people, according to statistics, today about half of crimes are committed by young people between the ages of 14 and 30 [18].

The high level of aggression and aggressive behavior in young people affects the emotional sphere of the individual, negatively affects professional and educational activities, interpersonal relationships, and is one of the risk factors for maintaining the health of young people. At the same time, the ability to flexibly emotionally regulate the hostile perception of social information and the anger reaction that arises towards it, as well as the development of self-control skills in adolescents, helps to limit their aggressive behavior [19-22]. Young people who seek to maintain close interpersonal relationships with parents and peers have been found to exhibit less reliably aggression. The severity of depressive states and affective disorders can in some cases cause autoaggressive behavior in young people. Research findings suggest that goals, skills, and behavioral strategies that aid or hinder violence are positively correlated in young people. In addition, a negative correlation was found between promoting violence and inhibiting goals, skills, and behavioral strategies [23-26].

The study of youth aggression found a high susceptibility, impulsivity, short-term and undifferentiated orientation of response to a disappointing situation, a link between family education and the level of aggressive tendencies, the manifestation of aggression in young people found that self-esteem is positively associated with cases of violence in childhood. when a child has witnessed or faced violence, in abused adolescents of borderline personality disorder, the internal component of aggression, which is determined by the characteristics of adolescents' adaptation to society, their individual psychological characteristics and the presence of aggressive tendencies in behavior, is formed from factors affecting the emergence and maintenance of aggressive behavior, surpasses the external component of aggression [37-30].

General characteristics of aggressive adolescents, among them poverty of value orientations, lack of hobbies, narrowness and instability of interests. For male adolescents, this is a feeling of weakness, fear, insecurity, for female adolescents – emotion, a feeling of fear in the process of communication, dependence. The increased sensitivity and vulnerability of such adolescents indicates psychological weakness and readiness of the individual for the appearance of various behaviors and mental disorders [31-33].

Aggressive behavior is seen as one of the forms of a person's response to various uncomfortable life situations that cause stress, frustration and other similar situations, and in this regard, in order to determine the individual and personal mechanisms of an aggressive reaction in students in a situation of frustration, we studied the personal, emotional and volitional characteristics of students and the forms of aggressive taking into account the degree of their impact on the frustration of the social environment [34-36]

The purpose of this study is to identify the psychological causes of the formation and spread of aggression in the youth environment.

Research methods and methods: Schmishek survey, SF-36 survey, Bass - Darky survey. Respondents Samdmu 1st year students (in 2 semesters) were 159 people. The data obtained was processed using the computer program Statgraphics 17.0. The Pearson correlation coefficient was used to estimate the relationship between indicators. Structure of the statistical population: by sex: 51,9% - boys, 49,1% - girls; by age: 16 – 17 years – 2,3%; 18 – 19 years – 69,4%; 20 – 21 years – 28,3%.

The results of the study: physical aggression has a direct weak correlation with a clogged ($r=0,170$, $p>0,05$) accentuation type; moderate with an unbalanced Type ($r=0,334$, $p>0,01$); emotional ($r=0,-214$, $p>0,01$) and disturbing ($r=0,-189$, $p>0,05$) type of accentuation. The level of physical aggression has a negative weak correlation with the indicators of the "pain" scale of the SF 36,242 survey. Indirect aggression has direct weak correlations with congestion ($r=0,196$, $p>0,05$), emotional ($r=0,212$, $p>0,01$), irritating ($r=0,223$, $p>0,01$), demonstrative ($r=0,193$, $p>0,05$) accentuation, and cyclothymic ($r = 0,193$, $p > 0,05$). Raised ($r=0,375$, $p>0,01$) and unbalanced ($r = 0,452$, $p>0,01$). A negative weak correlation was found between the indirect aggression indicator and the SF 36 scale: pain ($r=-0,209$, $p>0,01$), general health ($r=-0,273$, $p>0,01$), emotional activity ($r=-0,230$, $p>0,01$), physical component ($r=-0,176$, $p>0,05$) and psychological component ($r=-0,242$, $p>0,01$).

Irritation severity the degree of congestion ($r=0,252$, $p>0,01$), emotional ($r=0,230$, $p>0,01$), pedantic ($r=0,203$, $p>0,05$), disturbing ($r=0,283$, $p>0,01$), accentuation and cyclothymic ($r=0,431$, $p>0,01$), ascending ($r=0,388$, $p>0,01$) and unbalanced ($r=0,522$, $p>0,01$). A negative weak correlation between the irritation indicator and the SF 36 scale was found: role function ($r=-0,182$, $p>0,05$), emotional function ($R=-0,223$, $p>0,01$), psychological health ($R=-0,253$, $p>0,01$), psychological component ($r=-0,286$, $p>0,01$) and forces with moderate vital indicators ($r=-0,360$, $p>0,01$).

Verbal aggression is clogged ($r=0,267$, $p>0,01$), cyclothymic ($r=0,185$, $p>0,05$), unbalanced ($r=0,298$, $p>0,01$), elevated ($r=0,194$, $p>0,05$) with accentuation directly has a weak correlation.

The data obtained in the study show that accentuations are characterized by the following components of aggression and hostility:

- hyperthymic-doubt;
- clogged and unbalanced-all components of aggression and hostility;
- emotional and anxious-physical and indirect aggression, irritation and touch;
- pedantic-irritation and touch;
- cyclothymic and high-all components of aggression and hostility, except physical aggression;
- demonstrative-indirect aggression;
- dysthymic-touch.

Conclusions. The data obtained in the study shows that different accentuations are characterized by certain components of aggression and hostility. There are doubts about the hyperthymic type of accentuation. Individuals with advanced display characteristics are prone to indirect aggression, dysthymic - touch. The pedantic type of accentuation has developed aggressive components such as irritation and touch. Emotional and disturbing accentuation can be characterized as irritation and irritability, manifestation of indirect aggression, and a character trait with a low risk of using physical aggression. The components of aggressiveness and animosity developed mainly in young people with a clogged and unbalanced type of accentuation. With

cyclothymic and high accentuation, all components of aggression and hostility were developed, except for physical aggression. The correlation of physical activity is determined only by sensitivity, and social activity is determined by sensitivity and suspicion. As a component of aggressiveness, indirect aggression is manifested in people with a minimum level of role and emotional activity, general and psychological health (physical and psychological component), low vitality.

A decrease in the level of vitality and psychological health was found in people with severe irritation, irritability and suspicion. It should be noted that a decrease in the quality of life can be manifested by common asthenic and depressive states, which confirm the relevance of the problem under development. Thus, based on the data obtained during the study, the psychological factors of the formation of aggressive behavior in the youth environment include the type of accentuation of the character and the quality of life. We can say that when predicting the risk of developing aggressive behavior among young people the environment should take into account the quality of life of young people and the characteristics of their character. On the other hand, psychocorrectional measures should be directed towards these psychological factors.

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